

Smart energy demonstrator for energy communities

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Abstract—In the SERENE project, innovations to help improve integrated energy systems in local communities are developed. A key objective is to increase local self-consumption, particularly during peak solar production hours. These innovations are tested and validated in The Aardehuizen community, a neighbourhood which aims to be sustainable and self-sufficient. In this work the aims, development and preliminary results of three innovations are discussed 1) An energy storage system and associated smart control, 2) Smart control of e-boilers, and 3) An energy awareness app.

Index Terms—Smart control, ESS, E-boiler, Energy awareness, Energy community

I. INTRODUCTION

In the H2020 SERENE project [1], the overarching goal is to promote “Sustainable and Integrated Energy Systems in Local Communities”. In the Dutch demonstrator, located in the Aardehuizen community in Olst, the Netherlands, we aim to install, test and verify several technologies to enable smart energy management, and to increase the energy awareness of the inhabitants.

The Aardehuizen community is comprised of 22 single family households, with people who share the goal of having a self-sufficient and environmentally friendly neighbourhood. One of the goals is to increase self-consumption of the energy generated by 156 kWp of installed PV panels, evenly distributed over the neighbourhood.

In the SERENE project, we introduce, test and validate several innovations to optimize the energy usage and self-consumption in the neighbourhood, with the end-goal of reducing grid congestion, three of which are discussed in this work. 1) An energy storage system and associated smart control, 2) Smart control of e-boilers, and 3) An energy awareness app. These innovations are developed in collaboration with the Aardehuizen residents, and tested in their homes on a voluntary basis, hence not all innovations are installed in all households. This community driven approach results in the continued success of the demonstrator.

This work is structured as follows, required background is discussed in Section II. The three innovations are separately showcased in sections III, IV, and V. Overall conclusions and an outlook are presented in Section VI.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Energy usage monitoring

The successful operation of each of the three innovations requires access to detailed real-time and historical energy data for each household, as well as interfaces within devices to enable decentralized control. These complex requirements cannot be adequately addressed by conventional, domain-agnostic IoT or data monitoring platforms. Additionally, the system must support decentralized and distributed energy management systems (EMS) and demand-side management (DSM) applications, allowing for more efficient energy use and better integration within the community. It also needs clear unified data definitions and communication protocols for plug-and-play application management, such as EMS, dashboards, and market platforms [2].

To meet these needs, an overarching IoT framework called “IoT Edge Computing for carbOn Neutral communities” (IECON) was developed and deployed. It is integrated with a dedicated data monitoring system at the metering points of each household. In addition, smart plugs and interfaces were integrated into IECON to send control signals and monitor specific household devices, such as the electric boiler, neighbourhood battery, dishwasher, and washing machine. IECON collects data in a decentralized manner, with each household contributing to the overall system.

The framework incorporates lightweight architectures and communication protocols (HTTP and MQTT), and aims to provide high performance on restricted platforms, such as edge devices. Furthermore, the framework incorporates cybersecurity protocols to protect interfaces and communications, including secure data stewardship with data and algorithms managed on the edge. IECON aims to offer functionality that traditional platforms currently do not achieve [2], helping to avoid bottlenecks and ensuring the scalability needed for research projects.

B. Consequences of grid congestion

As grid congestion is an increasing problem as a result of renewable system integration and the electrification of loads (e.g., EVs and Heat Pump), enabling energy communities to be less dependent on electricity grids also helps grid operators to reduce grid congestion problems. One such problem is the increasing failure of transformers [3]. On July 18th 2023, the Aardehuizen community’s transformer failed, most likely due to long periods of high power export to the grid. As communities produce more of their own energy, reduction of transformer (and therefore grid) peak loads becomes necessary.

III. ENERGY STORAGE AND NEIGHBOURHOOD CONTROL STRATEGY

Energy Storage Systems (ESSs) in connected neighbourhood microgrids can provide flexibility to the DSO grid. In this work, we consider flexibility to mean an electricity grid’s ability to balance power production and demand under uncertainty [4]. One of the main objectives of the SERENE project is to investigate the technical, financial and environmental impacts of integrating an ESS to the community microgrid. Many of the lessons learned from SERENE will be applicable to other communities both in the Netherlands and throughout Europe. Furthermore, the control strategy of an ESS defines how it functions. In this project, we also investigate a number of different control objectives and strategies and their impacts.

For this project, the residents decided on an ESS after considering e.g. environmental impact of the ESS, the use of recycled materials and technical feasibility. From this evaluation, a standard solution using Lithium Iron Phosphate (LiFePO₄) batteries was chosen. They installed an 120kWh/60 kW ESS consisting of 26 Pylontech US5000 (LiFePO₄) [5] battery modules and 3 Victron Multiplus II-15.000 charge-controllers [6]. The ESS technology is fully developed, has predictable charge/discharge characteristics,

and is easy to interface with both existing charge controllers and self-designed control software. Furthermore, LiFePO₄ batteries are virtually non-flammable, making them safer compared to Lithium-Ion batteries. Finally, LiFePO₄ batteries contains no cobalt and nickel, which reduces the use of scarce raw materials.

While thorough testing of the ESS system is planned in last phase of the SERENE project, preliminary testing is already underway. As of the writing of this work, the ESS has been fully operational for 36 days (March 4th to April 8th 2025), which is the evaluation period for this section. This allows for a preliminary analysis of the impacts of using an ESS to increase local flexibility. Currently, the ESS uses no automated control strategy (e.g. Model Predictive Control), but is controlled by an operator that at the beginning of the day manually sets a (dis)charge profile for the ESS to follow based on weather predictions (and therefore a power generation prediction). Although this control strategy is somewhat rudimentary, it already leads to important insights. Note, that all measurement results are based on measuring power at 12 houses and the carport of the Aardehuizen, not the complete neighbourhood. While this unfortunately limits the conclusions that can be drawn, broader insights are still possible.

First, the power flexibility required from the grid after an ESS is integrated is analysed. In Fig. 1 the load duration curves of the microgrid imbalance load profile are shown before (P_{imb}) and after (P_{grid}) storage is applied. Fig. 1 shows that using an ESS to buffer energy reduces grid power utilization, especially power exported to the connected grid. However, it is also clear that the maximum grid export power (P_{grid}) is significantly larger than the maximum grid import power (P_{grid}). Table I further details \hat{P}_{grid} and \hat{P}_{grid} , as well as the percentage reduction of both in respect to \hat{P}_{imb} . Note that the total percentage reductions are with respect to the highest value over the entire period, and the day average percentage reductions are with respect to the highest value in each day, and then the average over all days. Regarding \hat{P}_{grid} , Table I shows that over the total evaluation period using an ESS leads to a significant \hat{P}_{grid} reduction of 28.57% total and 50.1% average per day. Regarding \hat{P}_{grid} , the ESS leads to a smaller reduction of 12.42% in total and 19.4% average per day.

Furthermore, to show how power peaks have been affected, Table I includes Peak Reduction (PR , Eq. 1), which is defined as the reduction of Euclidean distance of P_{grid} to zero (Ed^{imb}) in respect to the Euclidean distance of P_{imb} to zero (Ed^{grid}). The PR is 26.4% total and 33.3% average per day.

$$PR = \frac{Ed^{imb} - Ed^{grid}}{Ed^{imb}} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

Based on the power analysis, it is clear that the ESS leads to less power flexibility being required from the grid, although the export power flexibility required is still considerable.

First, the energy flexibility required from the grid (i.e., how much total energy must be able to be imported and exported) after an ESS is integrated is analysed. Total energy production and demand are considered separately, both over the evaluation period as well as the average per day. Furthermore, Degree of Autarky (DoA) and Self Consumption (SC) are considered, which are the dependence on a connected grid to handle energy demand and generation respectively. DoA (Eq. (2) [7]) is the percentage of the energy demand, which is consumed from local generation sources, while SC (Eq. (3), adapted from [8]) is the percentage of locally produced energy kept locally (including energy directly consumed by

Fig. 1. Load duration curves of P_{imb} and P_{grid} , 36 day period

loads and energy buffered in ESSs) [8]. In Eq. (2), E_{demand} is the total local energy demand and E_{import} is the total imported energy from the connected grid. In Eq. (3), $E_{prod,pot}$ is the total produced energy and E_{export} is the total exported energy. Note that energy amounts are aggregated over the evaluation period.

$$DOA = \frac{E_{demand} - E_{import}}{E_{demand}} \cdot 100 \quad (2)$$

$$SC = \frac{E_{prod,pot} - E_{export}}{E_{prod,pot}} \cdot 100 \quad (3)$$

Table I shows that over the period the community produces more than double the energy than they require over the evaluation (176.7 kWh average demand per day and 406.2 kWh average production). Note that the weather conditions during the evaluation period have been often clear, leading to high PV energy production. Furthermore, the ESS enables a significant increase in DoA of 44.2%pts total and 44.8%pts average per day to 92.8% and 92.9% respectively. The ESS also enables a significant increase in SC of 22.8%pts total and 25.2%pts average per day, to 44.2% and 44.8% respectively. Therefore, while the ESS allows for most of the energy demand to be provided by local sources, due to the significant overproduction of energy, the community is still quite dependent on the connected grid to handle this energy overproduction. Note that we think this will likely be the case for the majority of the period from March to October, but in the remaining months there is likely to be an underproduction due to less solar hours and a higher energy demand from the neighbourhood. Also, with a control strategy that actively reduces peaks, as well as the use of PV curtailment, we theorize that both the DoA and the SC can be increased further.

Finally, it is also interesting to see how the ESS is utilized during the evaluation period. Fig. 2 shows the State of Charge (SoC) profile of the ESS. Note that this profile was derived from the ESS load profile, and an efficiency of 91.5% is assumed [9]. Fig 2 shows that the ESS generally has a daily charge-discharge behaviour. On the majority of days, the ESS charges until it is (near) full, before discharging afterwards. When calculated exactly, the ESS makes 22.6 charge cycles over 36 days, which is about 0.63 cycles per day, where one cycles is considered to be the equivalent of a complete charge from 0% to 100% SoC. Furthermore, the ESS is not completely discharged often due to the overproduction of energy on most days. Therefore, a larger ESS may be required to better handle the significant overproduction of energy.

While the preliminary results show that even rudimentary control of an ESS can significantly impact the use of the connected grid, we theorize that greater reductions in grid requirements as well as financial and environmental benefits are possible using formal control strategies. Therefore, we wish to test how different control strategies and objectives

TABLE I
KPIs FOR POWER IMPORT/EXPORT AND SYSTEM CHARACTERISTICS

	P_{grid}^{\wedge} (kW / %)	P_{grid}^{\sim} (kW / %)	PR (%)	E_{demand} (kWh)	$E_{production}$ (kWh)	DoA (% / %pts inc.)	SC (% / %pts inc.)
Total	20.93 / 28.57	77.18 / 12.42	26.4	6360.4	14623.5	92.8 / 44.2	43.9 / 22.8
Day Average	10.7 / 50.1	56.4 / 19.4	33.3	176.7	406.2	92.9 / 44.8	48.8 / 25.2

Fig. 2. State of Charge profile of ESS, 36 day period

impact the microgrid and the community. Preliminary simulation studies on the impacts of considering single [10] as well as multiple [11] control objectives have been conducted. The results from these studies will be validated for the Aardehuizen microgrid during the final phase of the SERENE project.

IV. SMART CONTROL OF E-BOILERS

Electric boilers, also referred to as e-boilers, are electric appliances that consume energy to produce and store hot water for household taps. Every household in the Aardehuizen neighbourhood is equipped with an e-boiler for hot water needs. Typically, these devices operate with a simple internal control that ensures the availability of hot water. However, it can be advantageous if the e-boiler can be controlled more intelligently, i.e., the boiler should consume energy during periods of high solar energy production from PV systems and not consume during nighttime hours, when user demand is generally minimal. This requires information on how much energy is currently stored in the e-boiler (i.e. the SoC), but the boilers already installed in all the houses do not provide this information. Therefore, a Boiler Control System (BCS) was developed to enable the monitoring, communication, and power control of the e-boiler (see Fig. 3). Hence, the innovation here is the BCS which adds smart control features to any generic e-boiler.

Fig. 3. Overview of the e-boiler control system

The BCS adds temperature sensors at the water in- and outlet of the boiler, as well as a flowmeter at the inlet. Data

is collected using an Arduino that is connected and controlled via the IECON infrastructure (see Subsection II-A). The BCS provides simple on/off control via a relay. The comfort of the user has also been taken into account; at any moment they can take back control of their e-boiler by using the "big red button". Activating this button returns the e-boiler to the original (user specified) setting. The SoC of the boiler is determined using the temperature and flow measurements, and a model that was developed for the SERENE project [12].

In the SERENE project, two different control strategies are proposed. In the current phase, testing is being conducted using a rule based control strategy which uses basic conditional logic. The goal of this strategy is to move as much of the e-boilers energy demand as possible to moments where energy is being produced, thus reducing local power peaks as well as dependence on the connected grid. To achieve this goal, the e-boiler will only be allowed to demand power during certain hours, a so called activation window. However, hot water must be available to inhabitants when needed. To determine the e-boiler activation window, a survey was conducted among the participating residents, yielding average time slots when the residents need hot water.

To show possible results of a possible e-boiler activation window between 06:00 and 22:00, we have altered the measured e-boiler demand profile of a single household to conform to the activation window constraints, while keeping the total energy usage equal over the 24 hour period. Fig. 4a shows results from a simulation of power demand of the e-boiler in the original situation (P_{boiler}^{S1}) as well as in the controlled situation (P_{boiler}^{S2}), where we see that the entire energy demand outside of the e-boiler before 06:00 is shifted to the beginning of the activation window.

Fig. 4. a) E-boiler demand profiles and b) household imbalance profiles for April 12th 2025 (1 min data resolution)

The impact on the household power imbalance is shown in Fig. 4b, where we see that the power export for the first part

of the day has been reduced. Furthermore, the DoA of the household has been increased from 42.2% to 64.2%, while the SC has been increased from 26.0% to 39.5% ($P_{imb}^{\vec{S}1}$ compared to $P_{imb}^{\vec{S}2}$). Furthermore, the PR is 14.31%. Therefore, allowing e-boiler usage only during an activation window has the potential to decrease the households dependence on grid connection.

In the final phase of the SERENE project, two decentralized control strategies will be tested, in which operation of all e-boilers, EV chargers, and the ESS is coordinated. These strategies are the Profile Steering strategy [13] and the Advanced Arithmetic Optimizer strategy [11]. According to [14], controlling flexible loads can reduce the storage required to handle power imbalances. Furthermore, in the case of the Aardehuizen community, [15] shows that controlling the e-boilers as a group has the greatest impact on the ESS capacity and connected grid requirements, and that controlling all loads can significantly reduce both grid and ESS requirements.

V. ENERGY AWARENESS APP

The behaviour of residents, e.g when they choose to cook, do laundry, or charge their electric vehicles, influences when and how much energy is consumed. To encourage more conscious and energy-aware decisions, residents need clear and actionable insights into their energy usage, potential impact on sustainability, and consumption from the grid.

The same energy data that is used for research and system control purposes can be used to provide insights to residents. Based on IECON's modular and extensible architecture, a mobile application was developed to support energy-friendly decision-making and strengthen the community's energy identity. With secure authentication, users can view not only their own household data, but also aggregated information from shared community assets such as the community house, the carport (equipped with a large PV installation), and the neighbourhood battery system.

To ensure the app would be useful and inclusive for a diverse community with varying ages, backgrounds, and familiarity with energy systems, several co-creation workshops were held. During these sessions, residents could contribute ideas, give feedback on early designs, and draw inspiration from existing energy monitoring applications. This participatory process helped align the app's features with the real needs and lifestyles of the residents of Aardehuizen.

The most common request from residents was for a simple overview of each household's daily energy consumption, generation, and grid interaction, along with a clear indicator of self-sufficiency. More technically inclined users expressed interest in detailed visualizations of their energy data on an hourly, daily, weekly, and monthly basis. As the community aims to become entirely self-sufficient as a community, there was also a strong interest in accessing aggregated data at the community level, particularly for shared infrastructure such as the community house, the carport (where multiple residents charge their vehicles), and the local battery system. The app also provides insights in the energy usage of key household appliances, including electric boilers, dishwashers, and washing machines.

To accommodate varying levels of energy literacy, the app includes the option to display data not only in traditional units such as kilowatts and kilowatt-hours, but also in terms of CO_2 emissions (kg CO_2), which some users found more intuitive. These are calculated using the data provided by [16].

The app is organized hierarchically. The home screen offers an overview of the current performance of the user's household (see Fig. 5a), and a clear and accessible daily

Fig. 5. The app homescreen featuring a) the current performance of the user's household and b) a comprehensive daily summary.

summary. (see Fig. 5b). For users seeking deeper insights, additional screens provide access to more advanced graphs and analytics (see Fig. 6). The data is presented in a bar-chart of energy consumed and produced (Fig. 6a) and in a graph of the power profile (Fig. 6b). These graphs can be easily adjusted for a daily, weekly and monthly overview.

Fig. 6. Examples of more advanced analytics in the app, a) produced and consumed energy and b) produced and consumed power.

The application was developed to be compatible with the majority of mobile devices, ensuring broad accessibility among community members. Furthermore, a dedicated on-boarding workshop was organized, during which the app's functionalities and user interface were explained in detail. Residents were given the opportunity to create individual accounts, which were subsequently linked to their respective household energy data. Since the introduction, 26 accounts were registered across 15 households. Note, that all 15 households that currently have an EMS installed also use the app. Installations are planned for the remaining 7 households, it is likely that residents of these households will start using the app once installation has been completed.

Importantly, the application was also designed to be inclusive for residents without direct monitoring infrastructure, enabling access to data from shared community assets such as the community house, the carport, and aggregated community-level energy metrics. Statistics similar to those shown in Fig. 5 and 6 are presented for shared community assets.

The application received generally positive feedback from users, as collected through a structured questionnaire. Most users indicated daily use of the app, with some reporting behavioural changes such as shifting certain activities to

different times of the day or checking the app before starting an activity. Based on this, the app continues to be iteratively improved to better align with user expectations and needs.

An analysis of app usage data (see Fig. 7) provides additional insight into user engagement over time (developers and researcher accounts are excluded from this analysis). A significant spike in weekly and monthly unique users is visible in early March, marked by the red dashed line. This corresponds to a community workshop during which new users were onboarded and introduced to the app. The clear increase in usage around this event highlights how in-person activities and guided onboarding can drive engagement. While user numbers tapered off in the following weeks, a steady level of usage continued, suggesting ongoing interest and utility for many residents. Throughout the app's lifetime, the average number of unique users was 2.11 per day, 4.92 per week, and 7.14 per month, reflecting a steady core of engaged users who regularly interacted with the platform.

Fig. 7. Usage analytics in the app: (a) Weekly unique users and (b) Monthly unique users. Note that at the time of writing, data for July is only halfway complete.

However, the most persistent issue affecting long-term usage has been unreliable data collection. For some households, energy data was not consistently transmitted to the system, meaning users could not view their consumption information in the app despite the app itself functioning properly. This significantly reduced the perceived usefulness of the dashboard for those affected. Additionally, occasional bugs in the app impacted its overall performance, though these issues were less critical compared to the data problems. Although users could report these issues through the app, the complexity of the monitoring infrastructure made resolution challenging. At the time of writing, some data-related problems had not yet been fully resolved but were actively being investigated.

Further analysis indicates that user engagement has remained consistent, with residents accessing the application on a regular basis. To further increase user involvement and encourage more energy-aware behaviour, future development efforts will focus on the implementation of interactive features such as notifications and gamification elements. These enhancements are intended to facilitate behavioural change in a more engaging and user-friendly manner.

VI. CONCLUSIONS & OUTLOOK

In this work three innovations, developed in the SERENE project, are discussed. 1) An energy storage system and associated smart control, 2) Smart control of e-boilers, and 3) An energy awareness app. The common goal of these innovations is to help reduce grid congestion. It is demonstrated that

even rudimentary control of the ESS results in a significant increase of the DoA (44.8%pts average) and SC (44.8%pts average). It is also demonstrated that smart control of e-boilers, can help achieve similar results, with an increase in DoA of 52.1 %pts and in SC of 51.9 %pts. It is also concluded that the continued success of this demonstrator in the SERENE project is attributed to the close collaboration and co-creation with the inhabitants of the Aardehuizen community.

Future work consists of applying the control schemes, also developed within the SERENE project to both the ESS and e-boilers, it is expected that in both cases the DoA as well as the SC can be further improved. Future work also consists of improving the app and analysing how the behaviour of the users is impacted by its usage.

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